

The Academy of Business in Society

Highlights Report 2016

About ABIS

About ABIS

ABIS - The Academy of Business in Society is a global network of over 100 companies, networks, and academic institutions whose expertise, commitment and resources are leveraged to invest in a more sustainable future for business in society.

The ABIS Team supports its partners and members by harnessing the network's expertise, commitment and resources, and leveraging these through collaborative projects and events that empower change and deliver impact.

Mission

Our mission is to build bridges and strengthen collaboration between the corporate and academic worlds to accelerate systematic change in business education and practice. We create platforms and innovation spaces which enable our members to co-develop new knowledge, as well as education and learning frameworks, that will enhance the business contribution to society.

History

ABIS (formerly known as EABIS) was founded in 2002 in partnership with IBM, Microsoft, Johnson & Johnson, Unilever and Shell and with the support of the leading Business Schools in Europe (INSEAD, IMD, London Business School, ESADE, IESE, Copenhagen Business School, Warwick Business School, Vlerick Business School, Ashridge Business School, Cranfield, SDA Bocconi School of Management).

This creation of ABIS was driven by a shared belief that challenges linked to globalisation and sustainable development required new management skills, mindsets & capabilities. In order to respond to this need, the Partners made strategic commitments to develop Business in Society as a major field of research to underpin better education and learning.

Track Record

- Delivered 90+ knowledge development and learning initiatives
- Secured EUR 11+ million in EU grants to fund 60% of Corporate Responsibility research projects funded to date
- Invested EUR 2.5+ million in funding from ABIS' corporate founding partners and international foundations (UN Global Compact, Templeton, Roosevelt)
- Co-founded the UN Global Compact Principles for Responsible Management Education (PRME)
- Co-developed with EFMD the Corporate Responsibility and ethics-related criteria in EQUIS, the world's leading business school accreditation standard.

Message from the President

Dear ABIS Members,

I am delighted to share with you the highlights of another successful year for ABIS – The Academy of Business in Society and its international network.

Over the past years, we have witnessed the rise of tremendous challenges that not only business but society as a whole is facing. These are profound technological disruptions, transforming the world into a new digital age as well as severe climate and societal challenges.

These challenges have been the underlying foundations for recent talks at the World Economic Forum in Davos or at the WBCSD Council Member Meeting in Chennai last October, further demanding businesses to address these in a meaningful way. To do so, demands for new leadership are arising.

Our network has recognised this need for new profiles of business leaders, which is now manifested in numerous initiatives within ABIS.

These initiatives include our roundtables with Mazars that discussed the future role of the board and how the previously mentioned challenges result in strategic implications for their activities

within organisations. Two recently published reports are highlighting the results and implication both for academia as well as business.

In the similar regard, the ABIS Global Talent Forum which was first convened in December 2015 and chaired by Doug Baillie at Unilever's Four Acres Leadership Development Centre bringing together senior HRM, talent and leadership development executives from a range of global industry sectors. It opened new dialogues and reflection about the requisite talent to lead sustainable business transformation in a rapidly changing global context. After these informal discussions, a 2nd Forum last September focussed more deeply on Sustainable Business Leadership Qualities, by applying a framework by the University of Cambridge Institute for Sustainability Leadership under the facilitation of Dame Polly Courtice.

With leadership challenges not being mutually exclusive to Europe, our ABIS Corporate-Academic Partnership Programme in Africa aims to develop new leaders equipped with the right skills to lead businesses in the 21st century. Its first values-driven leadership workshops in association with Strathmore Business School and the University of Stellenbosch Business School in cooperation with IBM, GSK and Unilever successfully took place in Q3 last year. With this first workshop having been a great success, ABIS will not only continue this innovative form of collaboration but also expand it to other places across the continent in 2017.

Apart from these initiatives, 2016 has been a year where we have also harvested tremendous insights from our two large-scale EU projects. First, the EU-InnovatE project, which resulted in being a ground-breaking study into the emerging phenomenon of sustainable entrepreneurship and citizen innovation and the prospects for a sustainable Europe in 2050.

Secondly, the Innovation 4 Sustainability (I4S) project provided training and funding for 8 early-stage researchers and 2 experienced researchers to investigate sustainability-driven innovation in business. One of the key outcomes of this project is its final cases report which explores various dimensions of Sustainability-Driven Innovation.

To continue our success with EU projects, we managed to upscale our submissions to various funding schemes from previous years immensely. Last year's Knowledge Into Action Forum has been the source of 7 new project submissions, who applied for a total sum of over EUR 11M of EU funding.

In light of the above, I would like to thank all the ABIS membership for your continued support as well as the ABIS Advisory Board which congratulated the management team in their last meeting in November on the progress made and I hope that together with our dedicated ABIS team in Brussels, we continue to enhance the standing of our network and business in society.

I would like to close this message however on a more personal note and inform you that Simon Pickard is leaving ABIS this May after over 11 years of service to our organization and creating a meaningful impact by shaping the strategic ambitions of global organizations, leading large-scale projects, and shaping the business and society field as we know and understand it today. I would like to use this opportunity to thank him on behalf of the entire ABIS membership and the ABIS team for his outstanding contributions over the past years.

Sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Alfons Sauquet Rovira'. The signature is stylized and written in a cursive-like font.

Alfons Sauquet Rovira
President

EU Research and Innovation

Building Project Consortia

Empowerment of Business-Academic Collaboration

ABIS is committed to putting engaged business-academic collaboration at the heart of everything we do. It is our aim to be inclusive and demonstrate the value of ABIS as an innovation and collaboration hub for our members in different parts of the world. In this regard, we have focused in recent months on developing new ways in which members of the ABIS network can take greater ownership in bringing forward their inspiring ideas for new projects and engagement opportunities.

The online ABIS Members Area which was introduced in 2016 is designed to take us beyond the limits of physical events in Europe, and to empower members around the globe to connect and collaborate as never before.

Against this backdrop, the Knowledge Into Action Forum has evolved into the annual physical meeting between members at which the network has the chance to table ideas and discuss them directly to bring them forward as a project consortium.

ABIS Members Area

The ABIS website is now hosting the exclusive Members Area. This digital platform has been developed to reach out to academic and corporate members and connect them with each other. This online platform provides members with a relevant and useful content for engagement, as well as the opportunity to connect with every individual who is part of our network.

The Members Area accelerates proposal development in three essential ways:

- It hosts individual profiles of hundreds of managers and scholars inside ABIS member institutions, whose expertise is highlighted through a comprehensive tagging system – enabling members to find and connect directly with colleagues having common interest;
- It contains functionalities to allow members to post ideas or requests partners to develop new collaborative activities. Thanks to the tagging system, all members with a stated interest in the main theme are automatically notified of new documents being posted or conversation threads opened;

- A year-round notification service informs members of new funding and engagement opportunities linked to their areas of interest.

Members are highly encouraged to share and engage in new opportunities and manage their individual and institutional profiles. This again serves as an open loop system: members can be inspired to work together when new resourcing channels are announced, or develop multi-actor partnerships before looking for new opportunities for additional resources.

ABIS Knowledge Into Action Forum

In addition to our Members Area, we enhance the process of proposal development through our annual ABIS Knowledge Into Action Forum.

The forum is the main physical meeting point for the network to come together and discuss new ideas for collaboration at different stages of development. An interactive format allows for members to engage at three main levels:

1. A defined initiative for which project leaders are seeking key expertise and capabilities to address specific gaps and optimise the competitiveness of a grant proposal;
2. An emerging initiative for which the champions wish to test different approaches before designing concrete project plans;
3. Frontier thinking for which pioneers want to have exploratory discussions around new concepts and ideas, and to gauge network interest in developing them.

It should be underlined, however, that the Members Area exists to allow members to connect with each other at each level throughout the year!

In this way, the Forum is a valuable milestone: it is a focal point around which members can design their planning and project development, but it is also the potential catalyst for new partnerships which can then be developed ex post through the Members Area.

Support by the ABIS Team

As the development of projects and proposals can be quite challenging, the ABIS Team in Brussels supports members in a range of ways.

This relates in particular to European Union funding schemes, around which ABIS has a long track record and deep insights regarding key success factors and process management. As groups of members move into the more structured phases of proposal development, the ABIS team can offer its excellence in designing the Impact and Implementation sections of a bid – worth 1/3 of the final evaluation marks – and advise on the conceptual dimensions of proposal design. There are also resources available to help members prepare a consortium budget, and more broadly to leverage ABIS' institutional relationships to find network partners which can strengthen the bid's competitiveness.

EU Research and Innovation

EU Funds for Research and Innovation

Overview of EU Funding

European funds for research and innovation activities are distributed between several interlinked financing schemes. For the current period (2014-20), the main programme, Horizon 2020 is fully dedicated to funding such activities across all policy fields. Sectoral programmes also fund research and innovation activities in the fields of space research (Copernicus, Galileo); nuclear energy (Euratom Research and Training Programme, International Thermonuclear Experimental Reactor); and coal and steel production. The European Structural and Investment Funds, implemented at regional level, can be used to support the development of research and innovation capacities at local levels.

Combined, these schemes will invest an estimated €120 billion to support research and innovation activities in the period 2014-20.

Five other programmes are connected to, or impact on, research and innovation activities: COSME, Erasmus+, the Health programme, the Life programme and the Connecting Europe Facility.

In Education, the Erasmus+ programme aims to boost skills and employability, as well as modernising Education, Training, and Youth work. The

seven-year programme will have a budget of € 14.7 billion. Erasmus+ will support transnational partnerships among Education, Training, and Youth institutions and organisations to foster cooperation and bridge the worlds of Education and work in order to tackle the skills gaps we are facing in Europe.

Horizon 2020

With a current budget of over € 70 billion, Horizon 2020, the eighth framework programme for research and innovation, is the largest EU programme that specifically supports research and innovation activities. The programme is structured around three main pillars – Excellent Science, Industrial Leadership, and Societal Challenges – and provides funding through a large range of instruments and actions that ABIS supports its members with, for example:

- Grants to individual researchers for research projects or to support their mobility;
- Funding for cooperative research projects;
- Support and funding for public-public and for public-private partnerships;
- Specific instruments supporting research and innovation in SMEs.

Erasmus+

Erasmus + features three central schemes called Key Actions, of which two are particularly relevant for the network: Cooperation for Innovation, and Exchanges of Good Practices. Under the latter, ABIS prioritises the following opportunities:

Knowledge Alliances are transnational, structured and result-driven projects, notably between higher education and business. Knowledge Alliances are open to any discipline, sector and to cross-sectoral cooperation. The partners share common goals and work together towards mutually beneficial results and outcomes.

Strategic Partnerships are cooperation networks bringing together institutions/organizations active in the fields of education, training and/or youth, as well as enterprises, research institutes, public authorities, social partners etc. Strategic partnerships have the aim of cooperating in order to implement innovative practice leading to high quality teaching, training, learning and youth work, institutional modernization and societal innovation.

Additionally, the ABIS network has a great opportunity under Erasmus + to pursue new Joint Masters Degrees (JMD) around dimensions of sustainable business. JMDs enable an international consortium

of higher education institutions, plus industry and societal partners where relevant, to develop new programmes which fill key skills niches in the graduate job market and enhance sustainable growth and competitiveness.

Overview of EU Funded ABIS-supported Projects

- CSR Platform - EUR 750,000
- RESPONSE - EUR 1,100,000
- CSR IMPACT - EUR 2,600,000
- Business Case for Diversity - EUR 1,000,000
- Innovation for Sustainability - EUR 2,700,000
- EU-InnovatE - EUR 4,700,000
- Hi4CSR - EUR 80,000

Overview of Proposals Submitted in 2016

Since last year's Knowledge Into Action Forum in May 2016, the following project proposals have been submitted for EU Funding:

- Knowledge Alliance: ISODeM - Improving Sustainability-Oriented Decision Making 2017
- SOI4ESR 2017 - Sustainability-Oriented Intrapreneurship for Early Stage Researchers
- CO-CREATION-01-2017 - Young Entrepreneurs Scheme - YES!
- INNOSUP 07 2017 CISSME - Capability Innovation Scan for SMEs
- Evaluating the Transition to the Circular Economy: Models, Methods and Applications (TraCE)
- Blueprint for VET-business partnerships (BePartners)
- CSR and Ethics in Training Centers for the Benefit of all (CSREinTC)

EU Research and Innovation

Knowledge Into Action Forum 2016

New Knowledge, Approaches and Ideas

As part of the process to transform the embedded knowledge of our network into more collaborative projects (both in number and ambition), ABIS convened its inaugural Knowledge Into Action Forum in April 2015.

The Forum was conceived with two objectives: first, to grasp the increased opportunities to secure grants from the EU, through new schemes where members could propose the central theme instead of having it defined by the Commission; and second, to create a space for members to take more ownership and lead new proposals with their own areas of expertise and passion.

Above all, it aimed to provide an informal setting to give participants the opportunity to discuss international research proposals and fundraising possibilities in an atmosphere that fostered the active exchange of ideas and reinforced business-academia collaboration.

Knowledge Into Action Forum 2016

The second edition of our Knowledge Into Action Forum on 19 May, took place at the Management Centre Europe in Brussels. The one-day event's main focus lied on connecting our network around identifying new ideas and exciting project opportunities. The energy and ideas of individual members underpinned its programme, which included the following three blocks:

1. Insight Sessions – a corporate focused marketplace where small group or one-to-one meetings enabled corporate members to source new academic insights and thinking around emerging strategic challenges and issues;
2. Resource Opportunities – a helicopter view on a wide range of funding schemes and key success criteria to support business-academic collaboration;
3. Engagement Workshops – a series of in-depth roundtable presentations of concrete initiatives in development, through which their champions can find supporting partners, “reality check” objectives and materiality, and build awareness of their project within the network.

Event Proceedings

Based on the initial workshops, a number of proposals have seen further development for submission in 2016 and early 2017. The projects applied for a total of EUR 11M in EU Funding in the Horizon 2020 and Erasmus+ programmes. In this simple regard, the Forum can be considered a success – and our ambition is to double the number of workshop-generated proposals in 2017.

Many participants also underlined the value of having such a convening point in the ABIS calendar devoted to new project development.

Knowledge Exchange Sessions

Accenture: *New Skills & Competences for a Circular Economy, and the Implications for Business Education*

GlaxoSmithKline: *Global Leadership Development: Capacity Building Partnerships between Developed & Emerging Countries*

ING: *How Business Schools Educate and Develop Future Entrepreneurs for Sustainability*

Johnson & Johnson: *Stakeholder Strategy and Sustainability: Assessing Collaborative Impact and Defining New Governance Models to Increase Societal Impact*

Mazars: *The Future Role of Boards in Sustainable Corporate Value Creation*

Solvay: *Steering Product Portfolios to Higher Sustainability Levels through Science and Education*

Unilever: *The Sustainable Living Plan and New Models of Purposeful Leadership Development*

Engagement Workshops

University of Kent: *The Alliance for advanced implementation of collaborative solution*

Rotterdam University of Applied Sciences: *Innovating SMEs - segmentation along lifecycle and sectors (analytical research activity)*

Leuphana University: *Sustainability Quick-Check in Start ups and micro-Enterprises*

Nyenrode Business University: *Business and Peace*

Leuphana University: *Big Data Analytics for Sustainable Supply Chains*

I4S Partners: *Perspectives and practices of Circular Economy*

Coventry University: *Economics of Cybersecurity*

Stellenbosch University: *Responsible Management Education for Africa*

Audencia Business School: *Erasmus Mundus Joint Master Degree in Corporate Social Responsibility*

University of Edinburgh Business School: *Incorporating Sustainability in Management Education: An Interdisciplinary approach*

SDA Bocconi: *Impact entrepreneurship skills and competencies Labs Network*

EU Projects

EU-InnovatE

About EU-InnovatE

For the past three years, the EU-InnovatE project has investigated the prospects and obstacles for Europe to achieve sustainable lifestyles and a green economy by 2050. It has specifically explored the creative, innovative and entrepreneurial roles of users and citizens in developing novel sustainable products, services and systems in the domains of food, energy, living and mobility (“Sustainable Lifestyles 2.0”).

EU-InnovatE has been delivered through an innovative mixed methodology research design, as a reflection of the interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary complexity around its central theme. Qualitative and quantitative studies and analysis have been blended with a “co-creative” approach to ensure active stakeholder inclusion throughout.

The project has highlighted the potential power of people to influence transitions and change in existing systems. In particular, it has revealed the multiple roles that users and citizens play in catalysing a “new normal”, and the shifts in strategic corporate and policy thinking that would better harness the potential of this new phenomenon.

Key Outcomes

EU-InnovatE’s results provide compelling evidence of the increasingly active roles of users in sustainable transitions – either by taking part in sustainable innovation processes of companies (user-integrated innovation) or by starting their own ventures (sustainable entrepreneurship) – and suggest that firms and policy makers should place greater emphasis on enabling and harnessing user innovation and entrepreneurial potential.

At a policy level, our project has demonstrated the extent to which user innovation and sustainable entrepreneurship have the potential to play a significant role in addressing future societal and environmental challenges. However, sustainability and entrepreneurship have hitherto been addressed through separate policy regimes, which should ideally be unified going forward.

From an industry (and business stakeholder) perspective, in the context of an increasingly volatile, uncertain, complex and ambiguous (VUCA) world, sustainable innovation seems to be an imperative for business survival.

The notion that no business can succeed in a failed society, or in a world where natural resources are exhausted, is increasingly shaping European and global agendas. Disassociating growth from environmental footprints, while at the same time increasing positive social impact, is key to guaranteeing that present and future societies and ecosystems thrive.

To access and download the various publications, please visit: www.eu-innovate.com

Final Conference

On 22 November 2016, we convened the Final Conference of EU-InnovatE in Brussels. The conference attracted over 100 guests from business, academia and policy making it possible to engage with a lot of different stakeholders that have been part or have a vested interest in the project and its topics.

Throughout the day, the main findings of the project were showcased through various presentations and plenary sessions. Participants also had the chance for networking by bringing them directly together with people having similar interests and aspirations.

Participants also learned what it means to be a sustainable entrepreneur and what the European Union can and will do to bring companies forward that are leading the way towards a sustainable future for Europe.

Sustainable Entrepreneurship Award

Similar to previous years, EU-InnovatE continued its collaboration for the Sustainable Entrepreneurship Award (SEA) with future4you GmbH. The SEA was established in 2012 and has quickly become one of the world's most recognised platforms for identifying and rewarding entrepreneurs providing new solutions to global and local sustainability challenges.

Each year a range of awards are presented to enterprises, projects and ideas which address a social or ecological problem by combining innovative solutions with a profitable commercial strategy. A dedicated EU-InnovatE prize was now one of this year's gala event, with evaluations being conducted by a high-level jury chaired by Professor Belz, EU-InnovatE's Scientific Coordinator. The winners of the dedicated EU-InnovatE award were Leaf Republic who produce packaging products manufactured from leaves and bioplastic or recycled plastic.

EU Projects

Innovation for Sustainability (I4S)

About I4S

Funded under the EU 'Marie Curie Actions' and co-ordinated by ABIS, I4S was established in 2013 to equip Early Stage Researchers (ESRs) with the skills and competences demanded by companies, policy makers and academic research institutes, to assist the formation of our next generation of inter-disciplinary sustainability leaders and professionals.

The project came to its formal end on 31st December 2016, having delivered important messages and findings from the four-year training and research programme, at the I4S conference in Brussels, 28 October 2016. At the conference, the young researchers presented findings from their PhD research projects which ran alongside the four-year training journey. The integration of research and group training events, rotating around the partner institutions, formed the main pulse and organisational design principle of network's programme of activities.

The network came together around the concept of Sustainability-Driven Innovation (SDI) and the cohort of researchers applied the concept at different levels – from understanding the internal dynamics, values-centred leadership, or development of new business models within single large

multi-nationals; to understanding collaboration/competition dynamics at work across multi-actor networks and ecosystems oriented to sustainable and social responsibility outcomes. In each case, the researchers worked very closely with their corporate partners – using multi-method data collection and research techniques with a particular focus on 'Action Research' methodologies leading to concrete recommendations for the companies involved.

A key finding of the combined network research projects was to confirm that sustainability-oriented corporations engage in innovation in a proactive, stakeholder-engaging way, and at multiple levels. This might involve technological innovation, innovation in business models or innovations that result in systems change. The realisation of ambitions of this kind invariably involves businesses and others in product, managerial and organisational innovation simultaneously.

It was a huge honour, though an impossible task to fulfill, to follow in the footsteps of Nigel Roome. The best way we can celebrate and take forward Nigel's legacy is to collectively ensure the main messages and lessons from I4S are disseminated as widely and sharply as we can - Sally Randles

Dissemination

Professor Sally Randles, ABIS Scientist in charge for the I4S network, took over the role for the final year of the project following the tragic and untimely death of the inspirational I4S originator and champion, Nigel Roome.

During the final year the network achieved the notable success of securing the acceptance, then organising and delivering in August 2016 two workshop sessions at the 76th Annual Meeting of the Academy of Management in Anaheim, California. This is the premier world conference for more than 10,000 academics, students and professionals in the scholarly management and organizations space. The two I4S sessions focused on the research and pedagogy lessons and outcomes respectively:

- 'Innovating for Sustainability: The State of the Art and Beyond'
- 'Scholarship for Actionable Results: Reversing the Devolution of Care'

ACADEMY OF
Management

Since completing the project, the I4S network has been working to disseminate the lessons and recommendations from the last four years to three audiences:

- Practitioners who are committed to the development of new business models, products, process and services to achieve sustainability-driven innovation.
- Policy Makers who are committed to the development of policy that assists and supports sustainability-driven innovation.
- University doctoral training programme leaders, managers and academics who design and deliver inter-disciplinary training for the sustainability-leaders of the future; and policy makers tasked with assisting, supporting and improving Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions for the future.

All published materials, such as the project's cases report and different policy briefs can be accessed on the ABIS website.

EU Projects

Hi4CSR

Harmonization and Implementation of EU CSR Directives

Within the Erasmus+ programme and under the name Harmonization and Implementation of EU CSR Directives – Hi4CSR, ABIS is a project partner and participates in the first EU project oriented at the examination of the success of the EU Directives in the area of corporate social responsibility (CSR). The project officially began in October 2016 and will last until April of 2018. The main objective of the project is adult education and the exchange of examples of good practices between project partners when it comes to harmonization and implementation of EU Directives in CSR. The coordinator of the project is a leading Croatian company for accounting and finances, RRiF-plus d.o.o., with the following partners involved in the project as well:

- ABIS – The Academy of Business in Society (Belgium)
- Ekvilib Institute (Slovenia)
- Global Impact Grid (Germany)
- Institut za društveno odgovorno poslovanje (Croatia)
- LUM University (Italy)
- Pontis Foundation (Slovakia)
- Trucost (United Kingdom)

The project consists of seven main project activities. These are three one-day meetings and four five-day learning activities. During these different project activities, the partners will work on the development of the first CSR Guide that will in a clear and systematic way present the current status when it comes to the issues of EU CSR Directives, regarding topics such as waste management, food donations, eco labeling, non-financial reporting, the employment of people with disabilities, innovation, and the water framework. The project also aims to contribute to the development of sustainable policies and the strategy Europe 2020 through equal involvement and education of European enterprises, universities and NGOs.

The project has been opened with a one day meeting in Ljubljana, Slovenia, while the first five-day learning activity took place in Zagreb, Croatia, in January of 2017.

Learning Activities

The learning activities of the project are related to the need for a better understanding of CSR harmonization towards national legal frameworks. As all partners have a significant national reputation, professional knowledge and know-how, the added value of the project is to share specific knowledge and best-practices with other partners.

The main goal is for all project partners to have a similar knowledge and understanding of CSR and its harmonization according to the EU legislative. It is possible to say that the added value of the project's learning activities is to educate project partners who will receive the know-how of other partner's knowledge during the project in order to educate adults (enterprises, attendees of various programs, employees and decision makers) in their organizations and countries for project outcomes to become more relevant.

Learning activities in the project Hi4CSR will put a focus on the exchange of good practices of CSR harmonization to the national legal frameworks when it comes to relevant and important CSR directives in the European Union, that will have a great impact on society in the upcoming years.

Desired Outputs

This strategic partnership aims to produce collaborative CSR tools like a CSR Guide, video material, educative material for seminars and publications, blog, social media) in order to increase and be used for adult, enterprise and decision maker education and public conversation about importance of this subject.

More precisely, the project will result with a CSR guide for enterprises, adults and decision makers, a systematized know-how on CSR harmonization and implementation, in order to increase adult education and to develop new knowledge and skills on CSR topics. The Guide will show the current status and best practices in the harmonization of the EU legal framework among the project partner countries and will be the first comparative analysis study in the EU with examples of harmonization and good practice of CSR implementation in national frameworks. The Guide will be translated into all project partners' languages and used in educational, collaborative and consulting programs.

During the project accumulated knowledge of the exchange of good practices will be published in a CSR Guide and followed in an interactive media form. Online materials will be used as educational tools in the project partners' various educational and consulting programs (lectures, workshops, seminars, etc.). Video material on the project's Vimeo channel will be published showcase conclusions of every learning activity.

Hi4CSR

Harmonization and implementation of Corporate Social Responsibility EU Directives

Funded by

Partners

15th ABIS Annual Colloquium

Time for a new Agenda in Education, Learning & Talent Development

New Knowledge, Approaches and Ideas

The past 18 months have been highly significant in terms of the global sustainable development agenda. Acceptance has grown among political leaders, in particular, that urgent collective action is needed to tackle a range of complex, volatile threats to our biosphere and ecology.

As a result, intergovernmental commitments and policies around environmental and social issues – such as the COP21 Paris Agreement, which was just reinforced by the Marrakech Conference, UN Sustainable Development Goals and the European Union's Circular Economy (CE) package – have set out clear goals and targets to achieve by 2030. Huge opportunities await for business transformation and innovation: Accenture research suggests a US\$ 4.5 trillion reward for successful CE business models in this time-frame. Yet plenty of other question marks remain, such as:

- Do companies have the right people to grasp these opportunities in a responsible and equitable way? Do they understand the implications of digital transformation for their current workforce?
- What will the jobs in a circular, digital future look like?

- What kind of talent, skills and competences will be needed to support these by 2030?

Key stakeholders increasingly accept that these shifts in the global landscape will require a new paradigm in education and talent development, and new sets of organisational & individual capabilities. This is specifically true with regard to business education, given industry's role as a driver of innovation, jobs, growth and competitiveness, and business schools' role as a connecting hub between the sciences, technology, innovation, management, and more.

As we witnessed throughout the Colloquium, there are pockets of innovation developing in companies and in academia which may help to accelerate the development of dynamic new talent systems. However, the overall debate remains fragmented between public, private and civil sectors. International coalitions for change are very much in their nascent stages. And above all, the scale of today's economic, environmental and social challenges means that we can no longer wait to act.

In this context, the 2016 Colloquium brought together leading voices from industry, academia, youth communities and public policy – as well as those with related interests in global sustainability – to address three main issues, which ultimately framed the entire conference:

1. Developing a unified view of shared priorities for change among key stakeholders.
2. Adapting and scaling current innovations in business and academia.
3. Identifying successful business-academic partnership approaches that deliver measurable impact and change.

Speakers & Moderators

Doug Baillie
President, Positive Plant & Positive Economy Forum

Paul Begley
Programme Director, University of Cambridge Institute for Sustainability Leadership

Anthony Carey
Partner, Mazars

Luke Disney
Executive Director, INSEAD Centre for Social Innovation

Sherif Hassane
Director Government Affairs - Global Issues, GlaxoSmithKline

Kai Hockerts
Professor, Copenhagen Business School

Patrick Hull
Global Leadership Development Director, Unilever

Gary Kildare
Vice President, Human Resources, IBM Europe

Dean Van Leeuwen
Founder, TomorrowToday

Jens Meyer
Dean of Programs, CEDEP

Mirjam Minderman
Policy Adviser/Lecturer, Tias School of Business and Society

Petra Molthan Hill
Principal Lecturer, Nottingham Business School

Anita Negri
President of the Executive Board, Oikos International

Jan Noterdaeme
Senior Advisor, CSR Europe & Coordinator, Pact 4 Youth

Mollie Painter-Morland
Professor, Nottingham Business School

Maury Peiperl
Pro Vice Chancellor & Director School of Management, Cranfield University

Kaisu Puumalainen
Professor, Lappeenranta University of Technology

Annemieke Roobeek
Professor, Nyenrode Business Universiteit & Supervisory Board member, ABN AMRO Group

Kosheek Sewchurran
Associate Professor, UCT Graduate School of Business

Luk Van Wassenhove
Chaired Professor, INSEAD & Fellow of CEDEP

15th ABIS Annual Colloquium

Time for a new Agenda in Education, Learning & Talent Development

The Case for Systematic Change

The day of the Colloquium started with an opening plenary consisting a multi-disciplinary panel to address the need for systematic change in business and business education.

The session connected the business, academic, student and public policy perspectives on why this change is so important in times of tremendous risks and uncertainty. The panelists pointed out that in order for business to address these challenges, they need new talent and leadership profiles.

Corporate and Academic Interactive Sessions

It is clear that companies and education institutions will be at the forefront of building the new capabilities, skills and values that will underpin global sustainability progress. Both will however need to undertake a fundamental redesign of traditional approaches to ensure that sustainability is embedded in culture, hearts and minds within the organisation. Prior to the Colloquium, ABIS has spent a significant amount of time on its Education Initiative Report (see p. 31), mapping out how our academic members are currently developing

sustainable, responsible and ethical business education programmes. The feedback we received thus far highlighted the importance to broaden our inquiry into the drivers, obstacles and key success factors behind mainstreaming these issues across educational programmes.

To address this, the Colloquium featured two blocks of interactive parallel sessions – the first corporate, the second academic. These explored new approaches to creating systems of talent for sustainability, supported by insights from a new ABIS initiative or member innovation. The emphasis throughout is on people-driven debate and a systemic view of the main theme.

Some of the priorities that were echoed throughout the corporate sessions, were the integration of long-term value creation through understanding a company's impact on the wider ecosystem. One of the options to do so, would be the creation of collaboration spaces between organizations to co-create positive change. For these priorities to be carried out, it is relevant to identify and define the disconnects in the current educational system and to derive from this the necessary skills and competencies for future leaders in order to thrive in an ambiguous and uncertain world.

In order to transfer these, students should be exposed to problem-based learning and able to understand the purpose of business and their faculty as such. Furthermore, they should engage with various stakeholders of business in order to grasp the full context of sustainability-related issues.

Partnerships that make a Difference

The day ended with a final plenary session that highlighted the importance of partnerships that ABIS aims to foster over the year.

It highlighted how partnerships and co-creation can be the solution to tackle problems that otherwise may not be possible to solve. In this regard, examined the empirical aspects of successful partnerships in various domains such as health-care, policy and education as well as leadership development.

Programme

09:30 – 09:50 Welcome

- *Alfons Sauquet Rovira - President & Chair of the Board of Directors, ABIS*

09:50 – 10:00 Programme Introduction

- *Joris-Johann Lenssen - Managing Director, ABIS*

10:00 – 11:00 Opening Plenary: The Case for Systemic Change

- *Gary Kildare – Vice President, Human Resources, IBM Europe*
- *Maury Peiperl – Pro Vice Chancellor & Director School of Management, Cranfield University Presentation*
- *Dean van Leeuwen - Founder, TomorrowToday*
- *Anita Negri – President of the Executive Board, Oikos International Presentation*
- *Moderator: Doug Baillie - Chair of the Strategic Advisory Board, ABIS*

11:00 – 11:30 Coffee Break

11:30 – 12:45 Interactive Sessions: Creating Dynamic Systems of Leadership & Talent Development - Corporate Innovation Drivers

12:45 – 14:00 Lunch

14:00 – 15:15 Interactive Sessions II: Creating Dynamic Systems of Leadership and Talent Development - Academic Innovation Drivers

15:15 – 15:45 Coffee Break

15:45 – 16:00 Plenary Session: Partnerships that make a Difference

- *Mollie Painter-Morland – Professor, Nottingham Business School*
- *Sherif Hassane – Director Government Affairs - Global Issues, GlaxoSmithKline*
- *Jan Noterdaeme – Senior Advisor, CSR Europe & Coordinator, Pact 4 Youth*
- *Luke Disney – Executive Director, INSEAD Centre for Social Innovation*
- *Moderator: Jens Meyer - Dean of Programs, CEDEP*

16:00 – 17:00 Closing Session

ABIS Partnership Programmes

The Role of Boards as Stewards of long-term Value Creation

A Future Growth Agenda for Business Schools

In autumn 2016, ABIS and Mazars organised two high-level roundtables to explore the stewardship role to be played by Boards of Directors in creating long-term, sustainable corporate success. These considered the macro trends and challenges that business are facing from different strategic, governance and leadership perspectives, as well as the innovation prospects for business schools in terms of research, executive development programmes, post-graduate curricula and wider corporate engagement.

The New, Complex Global Business Context

Participants to the roundtables shared the view that business is facing a profound technological transformation, implying an extended period of rapid and disruptive change. For many established incumbents, it will be crucial for their leadership to understand and seize the positive opportunities offered by digitalisation and technology, while also responding effectively to the threats posed by it, including cybersecurity. Recent work by Accenture has highlighted five dimensions of digital transfor-

mation that are raising critical challenges for large companies and their Boards of Directors:

- New sources of competition
- Pace of disruption
- Impacts on society
- Increased transparency
- Potential to 'supercharge' existing sustainability-oriented products and services

International action on managing issues connected to global warming, biodiversity loss and natural resource depletion, as well as public health, demography and social exclusion, has started to move forward, both through the COP21 climate accord and the launch of the UN Sustainable Development Goals. While these pressures will significantly affect multiple industries, they also present huge opportunities for business to innovate in core products and services, and to strengthen engagement with governments as the lines of responsibility for framing and delivering solutions become increasingly blurred.

In fact, collective trust in business and political institutions has sunk to unprecedented lows since the financial crisis. New technologies and social media have empowered citizens, NGOs, regulators and institutional investors to look more deeply into corporate activities, leading to unparalleled demands for transparency on issues such as tax, corporate pay, human rights, lobbying and diversity. Firms like Unilever have suggested there is a profound shift in consumer attitudes underway with a potential 'tipping point' towards a much sharper focus on corporate purpose. Meanwhile, the social and environmental track records of companies are rapidly becoming a key factor for 'millennials' in their choice of future employer and a defining issue in the 'war for talent'.

Many multinationals have sought to increase their global reach in recent years despite their corporate culture, senior management and board composition remaining essentially anchored in one country. As the world shifts eastwards and – to a lesser extent – southwards in terms of population growth and share of world GDP, there is growing pressure on this to change.

New leading brands are emerging from Asia to challenge western incumbents, while cross-border mergers and acquisitions originating in the East are escalating, often with political support. Such trends seem likely to continue, but longer term uncertainties remain around, for example, the pace of China's future development together with the extent of population, health, demographic and environmental developments in many emerging and developing markets.

Assessing future Prospects for Business Schools

The ABIS – Mazars roundtables highlighted that business schools have not generally paid significant attention to Boards of Directors per se, with most research and teaching having focused on executive leadership and management. Yet institutionally they would seem to be well placed to provide some of the kind of independent, expert guidance on current and future trends that could help to effectively frame inputs to Board-level decision processes, and to provide cutting-edge training programmes. Stronger relationships with corporate partner Boards would also hopefully provide greater opportunities for publishable research and contributions to wider public debates.

The issues discussed during the round tables suggest a window of opportunity to broaden current curricula and disciplinary approaches / frameworks, with deeper integration of themes such as digital transformation, macro trends, global and corporate governance, boardroom culture and capabilities, and more.

Outcomes

The outcomes of the roundtables have been consolidated in two separate reports, highlighting the dimensions of the board's stewardship role in creating long-term sustainable success and the readiness of business schools to help address the future needs of leading businesses. If you would like to receive hard copies of these reports, do not hesitate to contact us.

ABIS Partnership Programmes

Talent Development for Sustainable Business

Redefining A Global Skills & Talent Agenda

In the past couple of years, a growing number of corporate sustainability champions – with Unilever in the vanguard – have recognised that they need new profiles from their talent pipelines to lead sustainable business transformation in a rapidly changing global context. However, they have significant challenges in finding, recruiting and developing the people that they seek.

The companies also recognise that, just as they cannot resolve sustainability challenges in isolation, they have a vested interest in consolidating and communicating their long-term talent requirements with a more unified voice, so that there is a strategic opportunity for business education providers to engage and respond through innovation in their own curricula and programmes.

In this regard, it is clear that the business contribution to sustainable development will be largely reliant on the qualities and vision of those who will lead their companies to deliver on their promises – not just at the top, but throughout an organisation. The central objective of the ABIS Talent Forum for Sustainable Business has been to explore how those qualities can be developed at scale, at pace, and in line with global ambitions for more sustainable futures for all.

Against this backdrop, it goes to the very heart of ABIS' founding mission – and the shared interests of our partners and members – to facilitate a new model of engagement between these companies and our wider academic network. Our ultimate objective is to inspire a deeper working relationship between the business and academic worlds, so that all companies benefit over time from graduate talent pools aligned with the global sustainability challenges we face.

2nd Talent Forum: Defining Future Skills and Qualities

After convening the first Global Talent Forum at Unilever's Four Acres Leadership Development Centre in December 2015, ABIS continued its efforts with a second Forum in September 2016.

Polly Courtice, Director of the Cambridge Institute for Sustainability Leadership (CISL), opened the Forum with an address focused on "Sustainable Business Leadership Qualities" – drawing also on the legacy work of CISL in this area and their breakthrough framework from 2011.

While underlining the severity and urgency of a range of macro issues, she emphasized that the combination of the COP process, UN SDGs, EU Circular Economy Package and more signalled a phenomenal business opportunity for agile, innovative, visionary companies, based on the indicative skills, traits and knowledge that will be required by the people who lead them.

Yet her opening remarks highlighted one of the more significant gaps in corporate capacity around the sustainable business agenda. While CISL has an incredible legacy in training more than 8K alumni through its programmes, almost none are working in HR & Talent Management.

Based on engagement with many corporate partners, there is a clear cognitive dissonance between sustainability in the core business and its implications for leadership and talent development. The business case has been made, but organisations now need to decide what kind of organisational culture and capabilities they will need.

The pace of disruption, emergence of new technologies and digitalisation, and more, will potentially lead companies down blind alleys. The best leaders will be able to filter and prioritise challenges and new business opportunities – with a focus on scalable solutions delivered at speed.

"It is in our collective interest to engage with leading business schools and management programmes, and to communicate our long-term talent requirements with a unified voice.

Our ultimate objective should be to inspire a deeper working relationship with business schools, so that all companies – not just Unilever – benefit over time from graduate talent pools aligned with the global sustainability challenges we face."

- Doug A. Baillie, Strategic Advisory Board Chair, ABIS & Former Chief HR Officer, Unilever

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ABIS Partnership Programmes

Values-Driven Leadership Development in Africa

Values-Driven Leadership Development in Africa

A Corporate-Academic Partnership Programme
Since 2014, ABIS has been partnering with various business schools in Africa to facilitate greater collaboration between Africa's Higher Education Institutions and business. Africa's flourishing economies offer fertile ground for the growth of entrepreneurship, innovation and talent. The key question that emerged was how to utilize these opportunities whilst taking into consideration the responsibilities that go with it. How could we better prepare talent for the leadership required to make progress towards building ethical institutions and sustainable development? ABIS, led by its Africa Director, Prof. Mollie Painter-Morland, and its corporate partners GSK, IBM, and Unilever, therefore set itself the goal to develop a cross-sectoral leadership development programme towards values-driven leadership for Africa, utilizing the world-renowned "Giving Voice to Values" pedagogy.

2016 was the first year of implementation as our partners and curriculum aligned with greater focus towards implementing our goal of developing a leadership course and piloting it through two ABIS's partner business schools in Africa. The title of the course that has emerged is "Values-driven Leadership Development for Africa" (VDL4Africa).

Cross-sectoral Collaboration as a Catalyst

The VDL4Africa platform aims to support responsible management education and leadership development for Africa's leaders within local companies, government bodies and NGOs. Collaboration between academia and all sectors is crucial for developing cross-cutting competencies in leaders. It is, in fact, a pertinent skill necessary to succeed in the fast-paced challenging business environment, especially in Africa.

The ABIS intervention addresses this issue by training academics to act as catalysts in developing these competencies around sustainability in all its facets and engaging leaders from all sectors in the VDL4Africa programme.

The first deliberate step in this direction was taken when ABIS brought together eighteen faculty members from seven business schools in Africa and four corporate partners for a two-day workshop on the 4 and 5 December 2015, at the University of Stellenbosch. The training process was facilitated by Prof. Mary Gentile who has developed a unique pedagogy called Giving Voice to Values (GVV). She says that GVV "challenges the assumptions about business ethics at companies and business schools, she argues that often the issue isn't distinguishing what is right or wrong, but knowing how to act on your values despite opposing pressure".

Key Objectives

1. Designing core components of executive, management and small business development courses on responsible leadership across the African continent;
2. Developing faculty to support the delivery of responsible management education and leadership education for sustainability;
3. Designing and delivering new innovations in management education at business schools as part of executive education offerings and through in company workshops.
4. Pilot 4 in-country training workshops in 2016-2017.
5. Start to roll-out successful VDL4Africa programmes across Africa in 2017-2018.

Key Milestones

Over the past few years, the ABIS Africa business-academic platform gathered through a series of workshops and worked together towards the common goal of designing a pilot course on leadership for Managing the Responsible Business Challenge in Africa. To design the building blocks of this pilot course, the platform has been focusing on:

1. Sharing current best practice models for leadership and management development in ethics and sustainability;
2. Facilitating strategic debate around the current gaps in leadership and management education towards sustainable and ethical business in Africa;
3. Designing core components, innovative methods and delivery structures of executive, management and small business leadership courses across the African continent.
4. Facilitating a two-day workshop to equip faculty to deliver content using the of Giving Voice to Values pedagogy.
5. Content and outcomes developed for piloting the course at two sites in Africa in 2016, and two further sites in 2017.

Considerable progress has been made - the framework and curriculum for the program has been written up and submitted for accreditation at the University of Stellenbosch Business School, three of our corporate partners, IBM, Unilever and GSK have committed seed funding to implement the two pilot programs in 2016. The pilots had the dual purpose of testing out the curriculum and facilitation methodology but also to double up as a 'train the trainer' opportunity for faculty from the schools in which the intervention takes place, so that they can continue to run it independently in years to come. The two successful pilots were implemented in 2016 at Strathmore Business School in Kenya, and by Stellenbosch Business School in South Africa, bringing together leaders from business, govern-

ment and third sector organizations for a 2-3 day executive development course. The success of the course rests on the adoption of a cross-sectoral approach, integrated from its design phase to the delivery mode and feeding back into the public discourse. It also requires us to sustain various communities of practice emerging out of the alumni of the various pilots and will allow us to study the impact going forward.

Research Opportunities on Impact of Leadership Development

The VDL4Africa platform was also successful in generating funding for further research on the impact of the programme. Led by Nottingham Business School at Nottingham Trent University, in cooperation with the American University of Cairo and Stellenbosch University, a successful Newton Fund ResearcherLinks Trilateral Workshop grant was written, which allowed the three partner schools to host a 5-day research development workshop for early career researchers from Egypt, South Africa and the UK in November 2016. An open call for expressions of interest was launched publicly, allowing researchers from various institutions to apply. The result was a research workshop that brought together researchers from the three countries to understand the 'Giving Voice to Values' (GVV) approach and to consider how the impact of such an approach may be studied in future. Researchers were introduced to the GVV pedagogical approach, and received insight into the pilots' structure and content. They were also supported with more general advice on career and publication strategies. We foresee that a larger number of schools can become involved in bid-writing and impact case studies going forward.

Future Outlook

The two successfully piloted programmes at Strathmore University and the other facilitated by the University of Stellenbosch Business School, are now ready to run the course by themselves. However, an experienced facilitator will still be on-hand to provide support and training to new in-country facilitators and ensure quality and alignment with the broader VDL4Africa platform goals. Two additional pilots are planned in Egypt and Nigeria in 2017. Further curriculum and content development will be undertaken based on the insights gained while delivering the next two pilots, and further faculty will be trained as facilitators.

In parallel, further funding opportunities are sought to allow us to achieve impact on a larger scale. Currently, bid writing is underway to allow us to explore pre- and post online delivery of certain course components going forward. This will allow the VDL4Africa platform to reach a larger number of African leaders in the next few years, and for researchers to more effectively study impact. ABIS will continue to strive to equip faculty with the content, facilitation skills, and the networks to allow them to successfully implement the VDL4Africa across Africa. The active platform that has been created to allow for a unique collaboration between many business schools and the private, public and third sectors, will continue to assist us in achieving this goal.

The Role of Corporate Sustainability in Asian Development

The Role of Corporate Sustainability in Asian Development: A Case Study Handbook (Forthcoming June 2016)

Editors:

- Dr. Fabien Martinez
- Prof. Hyuk Rhee
- Prof. Gilbert Lenssen

Corporate Sustainability (CS) has a short history in Asia, but is growing in importance. It can be defined as a business approach that responds to multiple stakeholders on every dimension of how a business operates and creates long-term shared value through integration of business strategies, human values, and ecological culture. It is logical that fast-growing economies, such as those in Asia, are boosted by the commitments of businesses to sustainable development of their regions.

Recently, more companies in Asia have started to recognise the strategic importance of building practices that create sustainable bottom lines related to the economy, environment, and society. Under-

standing CS as a part of the responsibility of a firm, extending beyond economic and legal obligations, multinational companies have sought to integrate new standards and norms that reflect the concern of various stakeholders, from consumers and employees to local communities. One such representative trend in CS is 'Fair Trade' in South Korea.

Other CS activities commonly practiced in Asia focus on philanthropic responsibilities, usually related to activities that enhance human welfare and goodwill in the respective regions. Most companies that carry out philanthropic projects make donations for such purposes as children or job educations, improvements in community infrastructure, and developments in art and culture. Eventually, CSR activities of multinational companies have been positively affecting the communities by satisfying various stakeholders and developing the social welfare as a whole. At the same time, the companies themselves have seen positive effects in the long term regarding brand image and customer satisfaction as well as financial performance.

It is against this backdrop that Korea University Business School and ABIS have sought to capture this emerging practice in a new case book for managers and business educators. The book titled: "The Role of Corporate Sustainability in Asian Development: A Case Study Handbook" builds mainly on the results of two conferences in South Korea in 2012 and 2013 that were co-hosted by KUBS and ABIS.

The conferences led practitioners and professors to discuss theoretical backgrounds of CS and later invited practitioners from leading global companies in the electronics and the automotive industries to discuss "The Role of Corporate Sustainability in Asia's Development," focusing more on the practical application of CS principles.

These corporate cases are now published with this book to showcase a range of best practices that have been highlighted as relevant in recent years and are certainly salient to address the role of corporate sustainability in Asian development.

The book which will be published later in 2017 will be useful to academicians who teach and research CS issues, practitioners who are searching for appropriate CS strategies to benchmark, students who are studying to be future business leaders in the field, and the general public who are interested in the CS activities of multinational companies.

List of Cases

- Intel – CSR 3.0: how to leverage social innovation to create business and social value
- Lenovo – Venture Philanthropy; supporting NGOs
- Samsung Electronics – Green Memory Chips
- ZTE – Eliminating Digital Chasm
- BMW – BMW I Story: revolutionizing sustainable mobility
- Hyundai Motor Company – Fostering social enterprises
- Mahindra & Mahindra – Mainstreaming sustainability in business through knowledge building

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ABIS Publications

Education Initiative Report

Sustainable, Responsible & Ethical Business Education

In 2016, ABIS has launched a new global Education Initiative to support the realization of its mission, to strengthen the exchange of institutional innovation and to drive change in business schools and universities to face the complexities and challenges of the 21st century.

As a first step, between February and July 2016, ABIS has focused on gathering and analysing data about full programmes dedicated to Sustainable, Responsible & Ethical (SRE) Business Education offered by its members. The overall objective of this phase was to map and estimate members' SRE educational offer. This report provides an overview of this mapping exercise.

A total of 152 SRE programmes have been identified. These are offered by 52 institutions, which currently represent academic partners and members, across nearly 20 countries.

A vast majority of programmes are offered at Graduate level (43%), followed by Executive Education (29%). Doctoral and MBA programmes reach a similar share, each representing 10% of the programmes. At undergraduate level, only 9 programmes have been identified (6%). Reflecting the structure of the network, programmes offered by European institutions dominate the educational offer (67%). Around 30% of the programmes are jointly offered by members in Asia, the Middle East and Africa.

In each of these geographic areas, there is a slightly different focus on various SRE themes. In Europe, "General Sustainability" is at the core of almost 40% of the programmes, but attention is also devoted to a wide range of other SRE issues. "Development Studies" (25%), "Social Impact" (25%) and "Social Entrepreneurship" (15%) dominate the educational offer in Middle East and Africa, whereas half of the programmes offered by Asian institutions have a strong focus on "Environmental Management". Overall, the offered programmes were most often associated with "General Sustainability", "Environmental Management" and "Sustainable Development".

This first analysis served to explore the cases where members have 'broken through the glass ceiling' of electives, stand-alone modules and events, and peripheral attention paid to Sustainable, Responsible & Ethical (SRE) Business Education. However, the scope of the mapping exercise was limited to full programmes without capturing those cases in which SRE issues are integrated across the whole portfolio of educational programmes.

Feedback we received from ABIS members highlighted the importance to broaden our inquiry into the drivers, obstacles and key success factors, such as interdisciplinarity and faculty development, behind mainstreaming corporate responsibility, ethics and sustainability as a way to capture and learn from the experience of those members which embarked on a strategic integration of SRE themes across its portfolio of educational programmes.

Considering the above, it is our aim to further address the mentioned issues and to share insights and solutions to overcome the obstacles posed by the mainstreaming of new education and talent development models in business and academia. We believe that the results of the present report are a valuable starting point to ignite this debate among our members. In case you would like to receive a free copy of the full report, do not hesitate to contact us.

ABIS Membership

ABIS Partners and Members

ABIS Partners

ABIS Members

Principles for Responsible Management Education

PRME Principles for Responsible Management Education

Overview

The Principles for Responsible Management (PRME) was launched in 2007 as a United Nations Global Compact initiative. It aims to globally inspire and lead change in the field of responsible management and thought leadership.

Inspired by internationally accepted values, which include the UN Global Compact's Ten Principles, the Six Principles of PRME provide a structure for engagement in order to advance academic institutions in terms of social responsibility by incorporating universal values into curricula and research. By doing so, PRME seeks to establish a process of continuous enhancement among institutions of management education in order to develop a new generation of business leaders that is capable of managing the complex challenges faced by business and society in the 21st century.

Gradual and Systemic Change in Business Education

The PRME initiative aims to create a framework for gradual, systemic change in business schools and management-related institutions. This change is based on three distinctive characteristics of the initiative: continuing improvement, a learning network, and reporting progress to stakeholders.

To report on progress of participating institutions to stakeholders through Sharing Information on Progress (SIP) reports is a crucial part of the active commitment to PRME.

Our Involvement

With ABIS being a co-creator of PRME, as well as member of its Steering Committee, we are part of the group of global and regional associations, which advise the PRME Secretariat on a wide range of strategic and operational issues.

Furthermore, as of 2015, ABIS' Managing Director Joris-Johann Lenssen is representing the ABIS in the PRME Steering Committee.

The committee as a whole is committed to advance long-term goals in responsible management education in business schools world wide. Finally, ABIS also aims to align our own initiatives with UN policies around sustainable development through the partnership with PRME.

Acknowledgment for Simon Pickard

With understandable regret, we would like to notify our members that Simon Pickard – ABIS’ Director International Programmes – will move on from the organisation to pursue a new phase in his career in the global sustainability domain this May.

As many of you will be aware, Simon has spent the past 11 years with ABIS, joining the Brussels team under EABIS Executive Director Peter Lacy in March 2006 after completing his MBA at HEC Paris School of Management. Over the past decade, he has played a central role in the development of the network, both in terms of organisation and of various flagship initiatives that have strengthened ABIS’ reputation as a thought leader in corporate responsibility and sustainability.

One of the most notable successes of his time with us has been the establishment of ABIS as a relevant actor in the European research landscape. After assuming coordination responsibilities for the breakthrough CSR PLATFORM project in 2007, Simon worked closely with Gilbert Lenssen - the ABIS President at the time - to ensure that its findings were integrated into the European Commission’s evolving research agenda, with political emphasis shifting from CSR to broader societal challenges (in line with ABIS’ founding mission).

In subsequent years, Simon played a vital role in securing other major EU grants for ABIS, including the “IMPACT”, “EU-InnovatE”, “I4S” and “Business Case for Diversity” projects. His ability to align emerging EU issues with members’ capabilities underpinned these successful proposals notably increasing in the number of members involved in collaborative proposal development.

By extension, Simon has worked extensively with various corporate partners and members to advance the corporate knowledge agenda in his time with us. Most recently he championed the “Global Talent Forum for Sustainable Business”, “Future of Boards as Stewards of Sustainable Success” and “The Alliance for Advancing Health Assets” giving new energy and momentum to ABIS’ work with leading global companies.

After so many years of deep immersion in the world of ABIS, we understand Simon’s desire to move on and find new challenges for the next decade of his career, and wish him every success in his future endeavours. We will undoubtedly keep a strong working relationship with him going forward, and are grateful for everything he has contributed to the ABIS mission over the years.

Thank you Simon for being a great colleague and source of inspiration to all of us!

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Karolina Sobczak
Projects Coordinator

ABIS - The Academy of Business in Society

Address

Avenue Molière 128
1050 Brussels
Belgium

Contact

+32 (0)2 539 37 02
info@abis-global.org
www.abis-global.org